
**NON-ARCHIMEDEAN WELCH BOUNDS AND NON-ARCHIMEDEAN ZAUNER
CONJECTURE**

K. MAHESH KRISHNA

Post Doctoral Fellow

Statistics and Mathematics Unit

Indian Statistical Institute, Bangalore Centre

Karnataka 560 059, India

Email: kmaheshak@gmail.com

Date: September 2, 2022

Abstract: Let \mathbb{K} be a non-Archimedean (complete) valued field satisfying

$$\left| \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j^2 \right| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |\lambda_j|^2, \quad \forall \lambda_j \in \mathbb{K}, 1 \leq j \leq n, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For $d \in \mathbb{N}$, let \mathbb{K}^d be the standard d -dimensional non-Archimedean Hilbert space. Let $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d)$ be the non-Archimedean Hilbert space of symmetric m -tensors. We prove the following result. If $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is a collection in \mathbb{K}^d satisfying $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$ and the operator $\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d) \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j^{\otimes m} \rangle \tau_j^{\otimes m} \in \text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d)$ is diagonalizable, then

$$(1) \quad \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \{ |n|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \} \geq \frac{|n|^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}}.$$

We call Inequality (1) as the non-Archimedean version of Welch bounds obtained by Welch [*IEEE Transactions on Information Theory, 1974*]. We formulate non-Archimedean Zauner conjecture.

Keywords: Non-Archimedean valued field, non-Archimedean Hilbert space, Welch bound, Zauner conjecture.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 12J25, 46S10, 47S10.

1. INTRODUCTION

Forty-eight years ago, Prof. L. Welch proved the following result [80].

Theorem 1.1. [80] (**Welch Bounds**) *Let $n > d$. If $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is any collection of unit vectors in \mathbb{C}^d , then*

$$\sum_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} = \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \geq \frac{n^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}}, \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In particular,

$$\sum_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \geq \frac{n^2}{d}.$$

Further,

$$(\text{Higher order Welch bounds}) \quad \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \geq \frac{1}{n-1} \left[\frac{n}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} - 1 \right], \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In particular,

$$\text{(First order Welch bound)} \quad \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \geq \frac{n-d}{d(n-1)}.$$

There are infinitely many applications of Theorem 1.1 such as in the study of root-mean-square (RMS) absolute cross relation of unit vectors [67], frame potential [9, 14, 18], correlations [66], codebooks [27], numerical search algorithms [81, 82], quantum measurements [69], coding and communications [72, 76], code division multiple access (CDMA) systems [49, 50], wireless systems [64], compressed/compressive sensing [1, 6, 29, 32, 68, 74, 75, 77], ‘game of Sloanes’ [45], equiangular tight frames [73], equiangular lines [23, 31, 44, 57], digital fingerprinting [56] etc.

Different proofs/improvements of Theorem 1.1 have been done in [19, 24, 25, 28, 42, 65, 72, 78, 79]. In 2021 M. Krishna derived continuous version of Theorem 1.1 [51]. In 2022 M. Krishna obtained Theorem 1.1 for Hilbert C^* -modules [53] and Banach spaces [52].

In this paper we derive non-Archimedean Welch bounds (Theorem 2.3). We formulate non-Archimedean Zauner conjecture (Conjecture 3.2).

2. NON-ARCHIMEDEAN WELCH BOUNDS

Let \mathbb{K} be a non-Archimedean (complete) valued field satisfying

$$(2) \quad \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j^2 \right| = \max_{1 \leq j \leq n} |\lambda_j|^2, \quad \forall \lambda_j \in \mathbb{K}, 1 \leq j \leq n, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Such non-Archimedean fields exist, see [61]. Throughout the paper, we assume that our non-Archimedean field satisfies Equation (2). For $d \in \mathbb{N}$, let \mathbb{K}^d be the standard non-Archimedean Hilbert space equipped with the inner product

$$\langle (a_j)_{j=1}^d, (b_j)_{j=1}^d \rangle := \sum_{j=1}^d a_j b_j, \quad \forall (a_j)_{j=1}^d, (b_j)_{j=1}^d \in \mathbb{K}^d.$$

Theorem 2.1. (First Order Non-Archimedean Welch Bound) *If $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is any collection in \mathbb{K}^d such that the operator $S_\tau : \mathbb{K}^d \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j \in \mathbb{K}^d$ is diagonalizable, then*

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \left\{ \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^2 \right|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \right\} \geq \frac{1}{|d|} \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle \right|^2.$$

In particular, if $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$, then

$$\text{(First order non-Archimedean Welch bound)} \quad \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \{ |n|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \} \geq \frac{|n|^2}{|d|}.$$

Proof. We first note that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tra}(S_\tau) &= \sum_{j=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle, \\ \text{Tra}(S_\tau^2) &= \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_d$ be the diagonal entries in the diagonalization of S_τ . Then using the diagonalizability of S_τ and the non-Archimedean Cauchy-Schwarz inequality (Theorem 2.4.2 [61]), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\left| \sum_{j=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle \right|^2 &= |\text{Tra}(S_\tau)|^2 = \left| \sum_{k=1}^d \lambda_k \right|^2 \leq |d| \left| \sum_{k=1}^d \lambda_k^2 \right| = |d| |\text{Tra}(S_\tau^2)| \\
&= |d| \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle \right| = |d| \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^2 + \sum_{j,k=1, j \neq k}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle \right| \\
&\leq |d| \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \left\{ \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^2 \right|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle| \right\} \\
&= |d| \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \left\{ \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^2 \right|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Whenever $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$,

$$|n|^2 \leq |d| \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \{ |n|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \}.$$

□

We next obtain higher order non-Archimedean Welch bounds. We use the following vector space result.

Theorem 2.2. [13, 21] *If \mathcal{V} is a vector space of dimension d and $\text{Sym}^m(\mathcal{V})$ denotes the vector space of symmetric m -tensors, then*

$$\dim(\text{Sym}^m(\mathcal{V})) = \binom{d+m-1}{m}, \quad \forall m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Theorem 2.3. (Higher Order Non-Archimedean Welch Bounds) *Let $m \in \mathbb{N}$. If $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is any collection in \mathbb{K}^d such that the operator $S_\tau : \text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d) \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j^{\otimes m} \rangle \tau_j^{\otimes m} \in \text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d)$ is diagonalizable, then*

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \left\{ \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^{2m} \right|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \right\} \geq \frac{1}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}} \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle^m \right|^2.$$

In particular, if $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$, then

$$\text{(Higher order non-Archimedean Welch bound)} \quad \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \{ |n|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \} \geq \frac{|n|^2}{\binom{d+m-1}{m}}.$$

Proof. Let $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_{\dim(\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d))}$ be the diagonal entries in the diagonalization of S_τ . Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle^m \right|^2 &= \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \langle \tau_j^{\otimes m}, \tau_j^{\otimes m} \rangle \right|^2 = |\text{Tra}(S_\tau)|^2 = \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\dim(\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d))} \lambda_k \right|^2 \\
 &\leq |\dim(\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d))| \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\dim(\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d))} \lambda_k^2 \right| = |\dim(\text{Sym}^m(\mathbb{K}^d))| |\text{Tra}(S_\tau^2)| \\
 &= \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| |\text{Tra}(S_\tau^2)| = \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \langle \tau_j^{\otimes m}, \tau_k^{\otimes m} \rangle \langle \tau_k^{\otimes m}, \tau_j^{\otimes m} \rangle \right| \\
 &= \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle^m \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle^m \right| \\
 &= \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^{2m} + \sum_{j,k=1, j \neq k}^n \langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle^m \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle^m \right| \\
 &\leq \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \left\{ \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^{2m} \right|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle^m \langle \tau_k, \tau_j \rangle^m| \right\} \\
 &= \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \left\{ \left| \sum_{l=1}^n \langle \tau_l, \tau_l \rangle^{2m} \right|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Whenever $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$,

$$|n|^2 \leq \left| \binom{d+m-1}{m} \right| \max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \{ |n|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^{2m} \}.$$

□

Remark 2.4. Theorems 2.1 and 2.3 hold by replacing \mathbb{K}^d by a d -dimensional non-Archimedean Hilbert space over \mathbb{K} .

3. NON-ARCHIMEDEAN ZAUNER CONJECTURE AND OPEN PROBLEMS

Theorem 2.1 straight away brings the following question.

Question 3.1. *Given non-Archimedean field \mathbb{K} satisfying Equation (2), for which $(d, n) \in \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N}$, there exist vectors $\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n \in \mathbb{K}^d$ satisfying the following.*

- (i) $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$.
- (ii) The operator $S_\tau : \mathbb{K}^d \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^n \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j \in \mathbb{K}^d$ is diagonalizable.
- (iii)

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} \{ |n|, |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 \} = \frac{|n|^2}{|d|}.$$

A particular case of Question 3.1 is the following non-Archimedean version of Zauner conjecture (see [2–5, 10–12, 33, 36, 43, 48, 51, 55, 63, 70, 84] for Zauner conjecture in Hilbert spaces, [53] for Zauner conjecture in Hilbert C^* -modules and [52] for Zauner conjecture in Banach spaces).

Conjecture 3.2. (Non-Archimedean Zauner Conjecture) *Let \mathbb{K} be a non-Archimedean field satisfying Equation (2). For each $d \in \mathbb{N}$, there exist vectors $\tau_1, \dots, \tau_{d^2} \in \mathbb{K}^d$ satisfying the following.*

- (i) $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = 1$ for all $1 \leq j \leq d^2$.
- (ii) The operator $S_\tau : \mathbb{K}^d \ni x \mapsto \sum_{j=1}^{d^2} \langle x, \tau_j \rangle \tau_j \in \mathbb{K}^d$ is diagonalizable.
- (iii)

$$|\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 = |d|, \quad \forall 1 \leq j, k \leq d^2, j \neq k.$$

We remember the definition of Gerzon's bound which allows us to recall the bounds which are in the same way to Welch bounds in Hilbert spaces.

Definition 3.3. [45] Given $d \in \mathbb{N}$, define **Gerzon's bound**

$$\mathcal{Z}(d, \mathbb{K}) := \begin{cases} d^2 & \text{if } \mathbb{K} = \mathbb{C} \\ \frac{d(d+1)}{2} & \text{if } \mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3.4. [16, 22, 41, 45, 58, 62, 71, 81] Define $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}$ or \mathbb{C} and $m := \dim_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{K})/2$. If $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ is any collection of unit vectors in \mathbb{K}^d , then

- (i) (**Bukh-Cox bound**)

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle| \geq \frac{\mathcal{Z}(n-d, \mathbb{K})}{n(1+m(n-d-1)\sqrt{m^{-1}+n-d}) - \mathcal{Z}(n-d, \mathbb{K})} \quad \text{if } n > d.$$

- (ii) (**Orthoplex/Rankin bound**)

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle| \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{d}} \quad \text{if } n > \mathcal{Z}(d, \mathbb{K}).$$

- (iii) (**Levenstein bound**)

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle| \geq \sqrt{\frac{n(m+1) - d(md+1)}{(n-d)(md+1)}} \quad \text{if } n > \mathcal{Z}(d, \mathbb{K}).$$

- (iv) (**Exponential bound**)

$$\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k} |\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle| \geq 1 - 2n^{-\frac{1}{d-1}}.$$

Theorem 3.4 and Theorem 2.1 give the following problem.

Question 3.5. *Whether there is a non-Archimedean version of Theorem 3.4? In particular, does there exists a version of*

- (i) *non-Archimedean Bukh-Cox bound?*
- (ii) *non-Archimedean Orthoplex/Rankin bound?*
- (iii) *non-Archimedean Levenstein bound?*
- (iv) *non-Archimedean Exponential bound?*

As written already, Welch bounds have applications in study of equiangular lines. Therefore we wish to formulate equiangular line problem for non-Archimedean Hilbert spaces. For the study of equiangular lines in Hilbert spaces we refer [7, 8, 15, 17, 26, 34, 35, 37, 40, 46, 47, 54, 59, 60, 83], quaternion Hilbert space we refer [30], octonion Hilbert space we refer [20], finite dimensional vector spaces over finite fields we refer [38, 39] and for Banach spaces we refer [52] (there equiangular line problem for Banach spaces is not mentioned explicitly but Zauner conjecture for Banach spaces is formulated. One can easily formulate equiangular line problem using that).

Question 3.6. (*Non-Archimedean Equiangular Line Problem*) *Let \mathbb{K} be a non-Archimedean field. Given $a \in \mathbb{K}$, $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\gamma > 0$, what is the maximum $n = n(\mathbb{K}, a, d, \gamma) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that there exist vectors $\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n \in \mathbb{K}^d$ satisfying the following.*

- (i) $\langle \tau_j, \tau_j \rangle = a$ for all $1 \leq j \leq n$.
(ii) $|\langle \tau_j, \tau_k \rangle|^2 = \gamma$ for all $1 \leq j, k \leq n, j \neq k$.

In particular, whether there is a non-Archimedean Gerzon bound?

Question 3.6 can be easily modified to formulate question of non-Archimedean regular s -distance sets.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. O. Alltop. Complex sequences with low periodic correlations. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 26(3):350–354, 1980.
- [2] D. M. Appleby. Symmetric informationally complete-positive operator valued measures and the extended Clifford group. *J. Math. Phys.*, 46(5):052107, 29, 2005.
- [3] Marcus Appleby, Ingemar Bengtsson, Steven Flammia, and Dardo Goyeneche. Tight frames, Hadamard matrices and Zauner’s conjecture. *J. Phys. A*, 52(29):295301, 26, 2019.
- [4] Marcus Appleby, Steven Flammia, Gary McConnell, and Jon Yard. SICs and algebraic number theory. *Found. Phys.*, 47(8):1042–1059, 2017.
- [5] Marcus Appleby, Steven Flammia, Gary McConnell, and Jon Yard. Generating ray class fields of real quadratic fields via complex equiangular lines. *Acta Arith.*, 192(3):211–233, 2020.
- [6] Waheed U. Bajwa, Robert Calderbank, and Dustin G. Mixon. Two are better than one: fundamental parameters of frame coherence. *Appl. Comput. Harmon. Anal.*, 33(1):58–78, 2012.
- [7] Igor Balla, Felix Draxler, Peter Keevash, and Benny Sudakov. Equiangular lines and spherical codes in Euclidean space. *Invent. Math.*, 211(1):179–212, 2018.
- [8] Alexander Barg and Wei-Hsuan Yu. New bounds for equiangular lines. In *Discrete geometry and algebraic combinatorics*, volume 625 of *Contemp. Math.*, pages 111–121. Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 2014.
- [9] John J. Benedetto and Matthew Fickus. Finite normalized tight frames. *Adv. Comput. Math.*, 18(2-4):357–385, 2003.
- [10] Ingemar Bengtsson. The number behind the simplest SIC-POVM. *Found. Phys.*, 47(8):1031–1041, 2017.
- [11] Ingemar Bengtsson. SICs: some explanations. *Found. Phys.*, 50(12):1794–1808, 2020.
- [12] Ingemar Bengtsson and Karol Zyczkowski. On discrete structures in finite Hilbert spaces. *arXiv:1701.07902v1 [quant-ph]*, 26 January 2017.
- [13] Cristiano Bocci and Luca Chiantini. *An introduction to algebraic statistics with tensors*, volume 118 of *Unitext*. Springer, Cham, 2019.
- [14] Bernhard G. Bodmann and John Haas. Frame potentials and the geometry of frames. *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 21(6):1344–1383, 2015.
- [15] Boris Bukh. Bounds on equiangular lines and on related spherical codes. *SIAM J. Discrete Math.*, 30(1):549–554, 2016.
- [16] Boris Bukh and Christopher Cox. Nearly orthogonal vectors and small antipodal spherical codes. *Israel J. Math.*, 238(1):359–388, 2020.
- [17] A. R. Calderbank, P. J. Cameron, W. M. Kantor, and J. J. Seidel. Z_4 -Kerdock codes, orthogonal spreads, and extremal Euclidean line-sets. *Proc. London Math. Soc. (3)*, 75(2):436–480, 1997.
- [18] Peter G. Casazza, Matthew Fickus, Jelena Kovačević, Manuel T. Leon, and Janet C. Tremain. A physical interpretation of tight frames. In *Harmonic analysis and applications*, Appl. Numer. Harmon. Anal., pages 51–76. Birkhäuser Boston, Boston, MA, 2006.
- [19] Ole Christensen, Somantika Datta, and Rae Young Kim. Equiangular frames and generalizations of the Welch bound to dual pairs of frames. *Linear Multilinear Algebra*, 68(12):2495–2505, 2020.
- [20] Henry Cohn, Abhinav Kumar, and Gregory Minton. Optimal simplices and codes in projective spaces. *Geom. Topol.*, 20(3):1289–1357, 2016.
- [21] Pierre Comon, Gene Golub, Lek-Heng Lim, and Bernard Mourrain. Symmetric tensors and symmetric tensor rank. *SIAM J. Matrix Anal. Appl.*, 30(3):1254–1279, 2008.
- [22] John H. Conway, Ronald H. Hardin, and Neil J. A. Sloane. Packing lines, planes, etc.: packings in Grassmannian spaces. *Experiment. Math.*, 5(2):139–159, 1996.
- [23] G. Coutinho, C. Godsil, H. Shirazi, and H. Zhan. Equiangular lines and covers of the complete graph. *Linear Algebra Appl.*, 488:264–283, 2016.
- [24] S. Datta, S. Howard, and D. Cochran. Geometry of the Welch bounds. *Linear Algebra Appl.*, 437(10):2455–2470, 2012.
- [25] Somantika Datta. Welch bounds for cross correlation of subspaces and generalizations. *Linear Multilinear Algebra*, 64(8):1484–1497, 2016.

- [26] D. de Caen. Large equiangular sets of lines in Euclidean space. *Electron. J. Combin.*, 7:Research Paper 55, 3, 2000.
- [27] Cunsheng Ding and Tao Feng. Codebooks from almost difference sets. *Des. Codes Cryptogr.*, 46(1):113–126, 2008.
- [28] M. Ehler and K. A. Okoudjou. Minimization of the probabilistic p -frame potential. *J. Statist. Plann. Inference*, 142(3):645–659, 2012.
- [29] Yonina C. Eldar and Gitta Kutyniok, editors. *Compressed sensing : Theory and application*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2012.
- [30] Boumediene Et-Taoui. Quaternionic equiangular lines. *Adv. Geom.*, 20(2):273–284, 2020.
- [31] Matthew Fickus, John Jasper, and Dustin G. Mixon. Packings in real projective spaces. *SIAM J. Appl. Algebra Geom.*, 2(3):377–409, 2018.
- [32] Simon Foucart and Holger Rauhut. *A mathematical introduction to compressive sensing*. Applied and Numerical Harmonic Analysis. Birkhäuser/Springer, New York, 2013.
- [33] Hoang M.C. Fuchs, C.A. and B.C Stacey. The SIC question: History and state of play. *Axioms*, 6(3), 2017.
- [34] Alexey Glazyrin and Wei-Hsuan Yu. Upper bounds for s -distance sets and equiangular lines. *Adv. Math.*, 330:810–833, 2018.
- [35] Chris Godsil and Aidan Roy. Equiangular lines, mutually unbiased bases, and spin models. *European J. Combin.*, 30(1):246–262, 2009.
- [36] Gilad Gour and Amir Kalev. Construction of all general symmetric informationally complete measurements. *J. Phys. A*, 47(33):335302, 14, 2014.
- [37] Gary Greaves, Jacobus H. Koolen, Akihiro Munemasa, and Ferenc Szollosi. Equiangular lines in Euclidean spaces. *J. Combin. Theory Ser. A*, 138:208–235, 2016.
- [38] Gary R. W. Greaves, Joseph W. Iverson, John Jasper, and Dustin G. Mixon. Frames over finite fields: basic theory and equiangular lines in unitary geometry. *Finite Fields Appl.*, 77:Paper No. 101954, 41, 2022.
- [39] Gary R. W. Greaves, Joseph W. Iverson, John Jasper, and Dustin G. Mixon. Frames over finite fields: equiangular lines in orthogonal geometry. *Linear Algebra Appl.*, 639:50–80, 2022.
- [40] Gary R. W. Greaves, Jevan Syatriadi, and Pavlo Yatsyna. Equiangular lines in low dimensional Euclidean spaces. *Combinatorica*, 41(6):839–872, 2021.
- [41] John I. Haas, Nathaniel Hammen, and Dustin G. Mixon. The Levenstein bound for packings in projective spaces. *Proceedings, volume 10394, Wavelets and Sparsity XVII, SPIE Optical Engineering+Applications, San Diego, California, United States of America*, 2017.
- [42] Marina Haikin, Ram Zamir, and Matan Gavish. Frame moments and Welch bound with erasures. *2018 IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory (ISIT)*, pages 2057–2061, 2018.
- [43] Pawel Horodecki, Lukasz Rudnicki, and Karol Zyczkowski. Five open problems in theory of quantum information. *arXiv:2002.03233v2 [quant-ph]*, 21 December 2020.
- [44] Joseph W. Iverson and Dustin G. Mixon. Doubly transitive lines I: Higman pairs and roux. *J. Combin. Theory Ser. A*, 185:Paper No. 105540, 47, 2022.
- [45] John Jasper, Emily J. King, and Dustin G. Mixon. Game of Sloanes: best known packings in complex projective space. *Proc. SPIE 11138, Wavelets and Sparsity XVIII*, 2019.
- [46] Zilin Jiang and Alexandr Polyanskii. Forbidden subgraphs for graphs of bounded spectral radius, with applications to equiangular lines. *Israel J. Math.*, 236(1):393–421, 2020.
- [47] Zilin Jiang, Jonathan Tidor, Yuan Yao, Shengtong Zhang, and Yufei Zhao. Equiangular lines with a fixed angle. *Ann. of Math. (2)*, 194(3):729–743, 2021.
- [48] Gene S. Kopp. SIC-POVMs and the Stark Conjectures. *Int. Math. Res. Not. IMRN*, (18):13812–13838, 2021.
- [49] J. Kovacevic and A. Chebira. Life beyond bases: The advent of frames (part I). *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 24(4):86–104, 2007.
- [50] J. Kovacevic and A. Chebira. Life beyond bases: The advent of frames (part II). *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 24(5):115–125, 2007.
- [51] K. Mahesh Krishna. Continuous Welch bounds with applications. *arXiv:2109.09296v1 [FA]*, 20 September 2021.
- [52] K. Mahesh Krishna. Discrete and continuous Welch bounds for Banach spaces with applications. *arXiv:2201.00980v1 [math.FA]* 4 January, 2022.
- [53] K. Mahesh Krishna. Modular Welch bounds with applications. *arXiv:2201.00319v1 [OA]* 2 January, 2022.
- [54] P. W. H. Lemmens and J. J. Seidel. Equiangular lines. *J. Algebra*, 24:494–512, 1973.

- [55] M. Maxino and Dustin G. Mixon. Biangular Gabor frames and Zauner’s conjecture. In *Wavelets and Sparsity XVIII*. 2019.
- [56] Dustin G. Mixon, Christopher J. Quinn, Negar Kiyavash, and Matthew Fickus. Fingerprinting with equiangular tight frames. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 59(3):1855–1865, 2013.
- [57] Dustin G. Mixon and James Solazzo. A short introduction to optimal line packings. *College Math. J.*, 49(2):82–91, 2018.
- [58] K.K. Mukkavilli, A. Sabharwal, E. Erkip, and B. Aazhang. On beamforming with finite rate feedback in multiple-antenna systems. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 49(10):2562–2579, 2003.
- [59] A. Neumaier. Graph representations, two-distance sets, and equiangular lines. *Linear Algebra Appl.*, 114/115:141–156, 1989.
- [60] Takayuki Okuda and Wei-Hsuan Yu. A new relative bound for equiangular lines and nonexistence of tight spherical designs of harmonic index 4. *European J. Combin.*, 53:96–103, 2016.
- [61] C. Perez-Garcia and W. H. Schikhof. *Locally convex spaces over non-Archimedean valued fields*, volume 119 of *Cambridge Studies in Advanced Mathematics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2010.
- [62] R. A. Rankin. The closest packing of spherical caps in n dimensions. *Proc. Glasgow Math. Assoc.*, 2:139–144, 1955.
- [63] Joseph M. Renes, Robin Blume-Kohout, A. J. Scott, and Carlton M. Caves. Symmetric informationally complete quantum measurements. *J. Math. Phys.*, 45(6):2171–2180, 2004.
- [64] C. Rose, S. Ulukus, and R. D. Yates. Wireless systems and interference avoidance. *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 1(3):415–428, 2002.
- [65] Moshe Rosenfeld. In praise of the Gram matrix. In *The mathematics of Paul Erdős, II*, volume 14 of *Algorithms Combin.*, pages 318–323. Springer, Berlin, 1997.
- [66] Dilip V. Sarwate. Bounds on crosscorrelation and autocorrelation of sequences. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 25(6):720–724, 1979.
- [67] Dilip V. Sarwate. Meeting the Welch bound with equality. In *Sequences and their applications (Singapore, 1998)*, Springer Ser. Discrete Math. Theor. Comput. Sci., pages 79–102. Springer, London, 1999.
- [68] Karin Schnass and Pierre Vanderghyest. Dictionary preconditioning for greedy algorithms. *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.*, 56(5):1994–2002, 2008.
- [69] A. J. Scott. Tight informationally complete quantum measurements. *J. Phys. A*, 39(43):13507–13530, 2006.
- [70] A. J. Scott and M. Grassl. Symmetric informationally complete positive-operator-valued measures: a new computer study. *J. Math. Phys.*, 51(4):042203, 16, 2010.
- [71] Mojtaba Soltanalian, Mohammad Mahdi Naghsh, and Petre Stoica. On meeting the peak correlation bounds. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 62(5):1210–1220, 2014.
- [72] Thomas Strohmer and Robert W. Heath, Jr. Grassmannian frames with applications to coding and communication. *Appl. Comput. Harmon. Anal.*, 14(3):257–275, 2003.
- [73] Mátyás A. Sustik, Joel A. Tropp, Inderjit S. Dhillon, and Robert W. Heath, Jr. On the existence of equiangular tight frames. *Linear Algebra Appl.*, 426(2-3):619–635, 2007.
- [74] Yan Shuo Tan. Energy optimization for distributions on the sphere and improvement to the Welch bounds. *Electron. Commun. Probab.*, 22:Paper No. 43, 12, 2017.
- [75] Joel A. Tropp. Greed is good: algorithmic results for sparse approximation. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 50(10):2231–2242, 2004.
- [76] Joel A. Tropp, Inderjit S. Dhillon, Robert W. Heath, Jr., and Thomas Strohmer. Designing structured tight frames via an alternating projection method. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 51(1):188–209, 2005.
- [77] M. Vidyasagar. *An introduction to compressed sensing*, volume 22 of *Computational Science & Engineering*. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (SIAM), Philadelphia, PA, 2020.
- [78] Shayne Waldron. Generalized Welch bound equality sequences are tight frames. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 49(9):2307–2309, 2003.
- [79] Shayne Waldron. A sharpening of the Welch bounds and the existence of real and complex spherical t -designs. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 63(11):6849–6857, 2017.
- [80] L. Welch. Lower bounds on the maximum cross correlation of signals. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, 20(3):397–399, 1974.
- [81] Pengfei Xia, Shengli Zhou, and Georgios B. Giannakis. Achieving the Welch bound with difference sets. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 51(5):1900–1907, 2005.

- [82] Pengfei Xia, Shengli Zhou, and Georgios B. Giannakis. Correction to: “Achieving the Welch bound with difference sets” [IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory 51 (2005), no. 5, 1900–1907]. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 52(7):3359, 2006.
- [83] Wei-Hsuan Yu. New bounds for equiangular lines and spherical two-distance sets. *SIAM J. Discrete Math.*, 31(2):908–917, 2017.
- [84] Gerhard Zauner. Quantum designs: foundations of a noncommutative design theory. *Int. J. Quantum Inf.*, 9(1):445–507, 2011.